

APPLICATION OF CONTINUUM DAMAGE MECHANICS TO POST FAILURE
ANALYSIS OF CFRP PLATES WITH HOLES

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ABSTRACT

A finite element analysis of the damage accumulation during uniaxial loading of notched CFRP has been performed. Two lay ups were considered : $(0,90)_s$ and $(0,90 \pm 45)_s$. The elastic case has been considered first, by using shell elements with superimposed layers. The results are compared with the experimental ones obtained at low loads. At higher loads, non linearities are observed due to mainly intralaminar and interlaminar damage accumulation. To modelize this behaviour, a numerical simulation of the tests has been made with the finite element code Abaqus. The capability of the code to account for a user defined material was used, first to define the elastic behaviour of the laminates, then to introduce damage with the help of the continuum damage mechanics formalism. Only progression of interlaminar damage is considered, but fixed delamination zone has been examined and their influence on stress profile, stress strain curves are compared with the experimental results.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic is currently used in the aeronautical and spatial industries for load bearing structures where requirement of safety needs an ultimate load analysis. For this kind of materials, stress concentrations and damage mechanisms in the vicinity of holes are very different from those usually found for isotropic materials. Many authors^{1,2,3} have been interested in this problem and have described the behaviour of similar materials in the elastic case. Though, many tests have shown that it is not realistic to estimate the failure of notched samples without taking into account damage evolution during the loading. The aim of this study is to introduce in the calculation of samples the different kinds of encountered damages and to evaluate their influence on the observed failure load values. In a first time, only the case of intralaminar matrix failures and fibre breakage is studied and tests are conducted with different lay-ups $(0,90)_s$, $(0,90 \pm 45)_s$ to follow damage evolutions and strains profiles.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Flat specimens were made from Ciba Geigy prepreg containing 914 C epoxy resin and Toray T6K carbon fibres and were cured in an autoclave at 180°C during two hours. The thickness of the samples were equal to 0,5 mm and 1 mm respectively for the four layers $(0,90)_s$ and the heigh layers $(0,90 \pm 45)_s$ plates. The gauge length of the sample was equal to 100 mm. Tensile tests were conducted in a screw driven Instron tensile testing machine at a speed of $0.2 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. The ratio $\frac{W}{2R}$ was equal to 6, where 2R and W are respectively the diameter of the hole and the width of the sample, the last parameter taking values equal to 18, 32 and 60 mm. A ratio of 6 leads (in the

elastic case), to a correcting factor CF due to the finite width of the sample equal to 1,03 defined as follows⁴ :

$$CF = \frac{K_T}{K_T^\infty} = \frac{2 + (1 - 2R/W)^3}{3(1 - 2R/W)} \quad \text{where } \sigma_N^\infty = \left(\frac{K_T}{K_T^\infty}\right) \sigma_N \quad (1)$$

$$\text{with : } K_T^\infty = 1 + \left[2 \left(\left(\frac{E_y}{E_x}\right)^{1/2} - \nu_{yx} \right) + \frac{E_y}{G_{xy}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

σ_N^∞ is the remote failure stress (based on gross cross sectional area) for a notched plate of infinite width. During the tests, strains are measured using photoelasticimetry or strain gauges. It should be specified, that in the vicinity of the hole, strain measurements were performed with gauges having very little grid surfaces (1,5 mm x 1,5 mm). Moreover, observations of replicas made on the edge of the samples and X radiography enable to follow damage evolution.

DAMAGE MODELING

1. Failure criterion

To separate the damage's nature, two failure criteria are used :

$$\text{fibre failure} = \frac{\epsilon_1}{\epsilon_{1u}} = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{intralaminar matrix failure} : \left(\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_{2u}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_{2u}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (4)$$

where ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 and γ are respectively the strain in the direction of fibres, perpendicular to the fibres, and shear strain. The subscript u are for ultimate values.

2. Damage accumulation

The consequence of these failures are of two kinds : firstly it appears a fall in modulus in the direction perpendicular to the fibres, secondly there is a reduction of the stress transfer by shear. To represent these phenomena, it is considered that the materials properties are modified by a damage state as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= E_1^* (1 - D_1) & \nu_{12} &= \nu_{12}^* \frac{E_1}{E_{10}} = \nu_{12}^* (1 - D_1) \\ E_2 &= E_2^* (1 - D_2) & G_{12} &= G_{12}^* (1 - D_6) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

and the proposed values of D_1 , D_2 and D_6 are :

$$D_1 = 1 - \exp \left[- \left\langle \left(\frac{\sigma_1^e}{\sigma_{1u}} \right)^p - 1 \right\rangle \right] \quad (6)$$

$$D_2 = 1 - \exp \left[- \left\langle \left\{ \left(\frac{\sigma_2^e}{\sigma_{2u}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^e}{\tau_{12u}} \right)^2 \right\}^m - 1 \right\rangle \right] \quad (7)$$

$$D_6 = 1 - \exp \left[- \left\langle \left\{ \left(\frac{\sigma_2^e}{\sigma_{2u}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^e}{\tau_{12u}} \right)^2 \right\}^n - 1 \right\rangle \right] \quad (8)$$

where : $\sigma_1^e, \sigma_2^e, \tau_{12}^e$ are fictive elastic stresses defined as follows : $\sigma_i^e = Q_{ij}^e \epsilon_j$ (9)

The parameters m, n, p have been identified on a $(\theta, 90 + \theta)_s$ laminate tested with θ equal to $15^\circ, 30^\circ$ and 45° .

The Figure 1 give a comparison of the obtained theoretical and experimental results. The Figure 2 gives a representation of mechanical behaviour of the individual ply for different loading with $m = 0,5, n = 0,29, p = 3$.

Fig. 1 Comparison between experimental and theoretical curve according to the presented model.

Fig. 2 Behaviour of the individual layer in shear or in tensile loading.

3. Calculation principles

A numerical simulation of the tests have been performed with the F.E. code Abaqus. Shell elements with superimposed layers and reduced integration were used. Each layer has a thickness and is considered as an orthotropic materials defined with the values of the constants $E_1, E_2, E_3, G_{12}, \nu_{12}, \nu_{13}$ and ν_{23} in its orthotropy axis and the value of θ , angle between these axes and these of the general reference.

The capability of the code to account for a user defined material was used to introduce damage. If damage occurs, the values taken by the elastic constants defined in the orthotropy axis are modified and the damage rigidity matrix and the Jacobien defined as follows :

$$[J_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \Delta \sigma_i}{\partial \Delta \epsilon_j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

are calculated in the general reference axis for these new values :

$$\text{with : } [\sigma_i] = [Q_{ij}] [\epsilon_j] \text{ and } Q_{ij} = Q_{ij}(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_6) \quad (11)$$

Using superimposed shell elements par each layer, it was possible to force the superimposed corresponding nodes to have the same displacement or not (in case of delamination). A subroutine was developed to manage such conditions as a function of delamination criteria ⁵.

RESULTS

1. Elastic behaviour

The used mesh is presented in Figure 3. The results obtained with the finit element calculations (Table 1) present a good correlation with the experimental results a low loading and with theoretical results obtained by using expression³ or Lekhnitkii⁴ approach :

$$K_T = 1 + \frac{B_1^2 + B_2^2}{(B_1 - B_2)} \quad (10) \text{ where } B_1 \text{ and } B_2 \text{ are positive solutions of :}$$

$$\frac{1}{E_x} B^4 + \left(\frac{1}{G_{xy}} - \frac{2 \nu_{xy}}{E_x} \right) B^2 + \frac{1}{E_y} = 0 \quad (12)$$

Fig 3 Mesh used for the calculation.

Table 1 Values of K_T for a sample with a hole.

	Expression 2	Expression 12	F.E. calculation
$(0,90)_s$	4,98	4,95	5
$(0,90 \pm 45)_s$	3	3	2,95

Elastic stress profiles in the weakest section, stress contours obtained from the calculations and strain contours obtained from photoelasticity measurement have been compared⁶. These comparisons show that the calculations provide a good approximation of the samples behaviour a low stress level.

2. Damaged behaviour

When the samples behaviour stop being elastic, different non linearities on the curves (strain-load) may be observed. Practically, all the behaviour modifications are the consequences of local loss of material properties and of stress redistributions due to damage evolution⁷: matrix failure parallel to the fibres in the different ply orientations and delamination near the hole and in areas where high fissuration densities exist in two adjacent plies (Figure 4).

On Figure 5, the experimental behaviour and the corresponding modeling of the $(0,90 \pm 45)_s$ sample are presented and a good correspondance can be found. It should be noticed, that the behaviour is almost linear : the accumulation of damage before catastrophic failure is rather low compare to the amount of accumulated damage in the $(0,90)_s$ sample. For this later material, the non linearities are much more important. It has been found that the above modelisation was able to describe qualitatively the behaviour (Figure 6). It has been thought that the difference could be explained by delamination as shown in Figure 4.

To account for this phenomenon, a new simulation has been undertaken with different areas of delamination determined by the X-ray observations. One can noticed a better tendency. (figure 6). The persistent difference between the experimental results and the modelisation could be explained by the fact that the behaviour of the damaged layer is not intrinsic but depends on the lay-up in which it is located. If the environment of the layer is changed - by delamination for example - its behaviour will change and the corresponding parametres m , n , p for example will be different of those determined in uniaxial tension on samples where no delaminations has been found.

Fig 4 X-ray investigation of the damage state of a $(0,90)_s$ sample.

Fig 5 Comparison between experimental and theoretical deformations obtained at different location around the hole in the $(0, 90, \pm 45)_s$ sample. No delaminations are taking into account.

Fig 6 Comparison between experimental and theoretical deformations obtained at different location around the hole in the $(0, 90)_s$ with (-■-) or without (-□-) delamination taken into account.

CONCLUSION

During these investigation, the complexity of the interaction between the different mechanisms of degradation appeared very clearly both from the numerical and from the experimental point of view. This approach could be used to determine the load at failure of notched structures for example. Two possibilities could be considered : the first one is to improved the average or the point stress criterion proposed by Whitney and Nuismer (8) by using the real stress profile in the weakest section, the second could be based on an instability criteria.

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